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Development of Leadership Abilities of Students in Pedagogical Higher Education-A Requirement of the New Time

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***Abstract:** In the modern higher education system, the development of leadership skills in students holds significant importance today. This article is dedicated to the demands of the modern era, analyzing the social-pedagogical necessity of developing leadership skills and effective methods for instilling these skills in students. By examining the distinctive features of shaping leadership in higher education institutions, the article explores the role of a leader in the educational process, development factors, and applied methodological approaches. Additionally, the article outlines ways to develop key competencies in students such as initiative, responsibility, communication competence, and team management. The research process establishes the theoretical and practical foundations for introducing innovative pedagogical methods into higher education and shaping leadership activities. The article also thoroughly discusses modern approaches, including interactive teaching methods, the integration of digital technologies, and moral values.*

***Key words:** higher education, leadership skills, educational process, pedagogical methodology, innovative approaches, communication competence, social-pedagogical necessity.*

Introduction: It is emphasized that one of the important tasks of the 21st-century education system is the training of specialists with personal leadership abilities. In higher education, leadership abilities are important not only in the field of management, but also in various types of professional activity. Therefore, the formation and development of students' leadership skills in higher educational institutions is becoming an integral part of the pedagogical process. After all, today the introduction of advanced pedagogical methods and innovative technologies for the development of leadership abilities into the educational process is a social and pedagogical necessity. In the context of globalization and

competition, the growing demand for specialists possessing not only knowledge but also independent thinking, problem-solving, teamwork, and initiative is clear evidence of this.

In particular, considering that the development of Uzbekistan largely depends on the younger generation, in particular, students, through the rational use of the conditions created by the state, young people should not only achieve personal perfection, but also serve as an example for other members of society. Although the problem of youth unemployment remains relevant on a global scale, the state policy aimed at youth in Uzbekistan creates the basis for their success in various fields.

Therefore, our research is aimed at analyzing the socio-pedagogical aspects, methodological foundations, and practical directions of the development of students' leadership abilities. In particular, based on scientific literature, experience, and advanced educational technologies, effective pedagogical methods that contribute to the formation of students' leadership abilities are proposed. In the course of our research, we will pay attention to the definition of the methodology for the development of leadership abilities, given by scientists of foreign countries.

Leadership is an individual's ability to direct others, make decisions, take initiative, and take responsibility (Bass, 1990). In the modern education system, the development of students' leadership abilities not only increases their professional training, but is also important for their active and effective participation in society. According to another researcher, leadership is important because it strengthens trust among the members of the organization and stimulates a professional and creative environment.

Today, science, especially the socio-psychological sphere, is developing rapidly. Regarding the meaning of the word "leadership," in the Uzbek language this word means "leadership," "leadership," or "management." This word usually means to manage a group, society, or organization, to guide them, and to motivate them to achieve their goals. The historical roots of the word go back to the group of Turkic languages and have been associated with the concepts of leadership, governance, leadership, and guidance among the Turkic peoples since ancient times. Consequently, the connection between the student's personal abilities and the opportunities created by time is an important factor in the development of leadership abilities. This article aims to study pedagogical and psychological methods and provide recommendations for the formation of leadership abilities in students.

Studies show that students' leadership abilities are developed under the influence of the following factors:

- Independent thinking and problem-solving skills;
- Initiative and creative approach;
- Teamwork and communicative competencies;
- Critical thinking and decision-making ability (Kouzes & Posner, 2017).

In the process of higher education, various pedagogical methods can be used to form leadership skills. In particular, project-based learning, problem-based learning, practical seminars, and methods of group work play an important role in the development of leadership abilities. It is recommended to use the following pedagogical approaches, which are considered important for the development of leadership abilities in the higher education system:

- Project-based learning - the development of students' creative and leadership abilities, directing them to solve real-life problems.

- Entrepreneurship and business training - preparing students for leadership through the formation of innovative thinking and entrepreneurial skills (Goleman, 1998).
- Mentoring programs - involving students in leadership processes by working with experienced leaders.
- These methods directly contribute to the development of leadership abilities in students studying in higher education.

Target: The development of leadership abilities in students has been identified as a necessity and requirement of the new era in higher education.

Materials and methods: The research can utilize mixed methods combining quantitative and qualitative approaches. Materials include course programs, curricula, online learning platforms, assessment tools, and others. Methods involve surveys of educators and students, observation of practical sessions, and analysis of student activity data.

Discussion and results: Through early development of leadership potential in students, they should gain a deep understanding of the true essence of management systems. Moreover, it becomes possible to cultivate from a young age the qualities that are crucial for future managers and leaders, such as experience, qualifications, skills, knowledge, intelligence, breadth of thinking, perceptiveness, and most importantly, integrity, work dedication, good nature, purity of heart, sense of justice, and resistance to base desires. Significantly, this process allows them to test their knowledge and skills in small teams and gain experience before being appointed to official leadership positions.

Conclusion: Our conclusion indicates that the socio-pedagogical need for developing students' leadership abilities in higher educational institutions is increasingly growing. Leadership skills are important not only for personal development but also for professional success and overall societal progress. This study analyzed ways of fostering leadership abilities through pedagogical methods, innovative technologies, and interactive approaches. Our research demonstrates the critical importance of developing leadership abilities in students, especially future educators, within the modern education system. The methodologies and approaches proposed in the article are highly useful and valuable for practical implementation.

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